

A Silicon-Based Optical Signal Transmitter for Sub-THz Wireless Communication Systems

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Abstract — We present the compact integration of an optical heterodyne-based terahertz transmitter in silicon, including ring filters and a dual-parallel Mach Zehnder modulator. The transmitter module has a footprint area of 2.4x0.4 mm and is integrated into the open-access Tower’s PH18MA silicon photonics platform. Ring-based bandpass filters and single Mach Zehnder modulator, essentials building blocks of an optical heterodyne system, feature the following: high wavelength selectivity over a 100 GHz free spectral range and intensity modulation capabilities performing a data transmission test, respectively. This study reveals the potential of this state-of-the-art integration platform to enable complex transmitter modules based on silicon for high-speed operation, low phase noise thanks to the phase-locking scheme via ring filters and flexible multi-level modulation formats.

Keywords — silicon photonics, sub-THz, optical signal generation, wavelength filters, Mach Zehnder modulator.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sub-THz communications based on photonic integrated circuits have enabled high-capacity and broadband wireless channels via compact systems. Comparing to all-electronic systems, photonically assisted circuits offer high-performance and power-efficient signal processing, wide bandwidth, and low loss transmission [1]. All these key aspects are critical parameters to create robust wireless links for high data rate transmission. Therefore, the selection of the optical transmitter module is crucial since it strongly affects the quality and spectral purity of the output RF signal. A promising optical generation approach is the optical heterodyne beating of two individual wavelength-tunable laser sources on an optical-to-electronic converter to directly generate the RF signal [1], [2]. These integrated systems require an active section to host the laser sources, such as Indium Phosphide (InP) platform which has advantages of wide tuning frequency range and high-performance RF signal [3]. Despite its advantages, InP-based transmitters require phase-locking techniques to reduce the frequency drift and widening of the beat-note signal due to temperature variations. Optical injection can be efficiently used to phase-lock the two optical wavelengths and generate an ultra-stable RF signal at 93 GHz [4]. On the other hand, heterogenous InP/Silicon integration approach is being introduced as the key technology to achieve fully integrated photonic systems combining high performance silicon passive

elements for efficient phase locking schemes [5] and InP-based active gain sections.

Silicon photonics (SiPh) platform has been employed to provide power efficient optical interconnects, such as high-speed modulators [6], high-performance and low loss passive circuits for critical light manipulation in THz domain [5]. As part of the solution, silicon-based integrated circuits display the following key aspects: low loss waveguide transmission (< 2 dB/cm) [5], low-cost production and high system complexity on large scale wafers and CMOS compatibility enabling complete THz system solutions for data communication [7].

This study presents a silicon optical transmitter module to enable wireless communications from 100 GHz and beyond. To overcome the limitations from the dual laser source, as previously described, cascaded second-order ring filters are introduced as a phase locking scheme to offer high frequency stability and broadband operation. The integrated transmitter module is designed and fabricated on a novel SiPh platform operating in a heterodyne scheme and enabling advanced signal processing capabilities.

II. SUB-THz TRANSMITTER ARCHITECTURE

Silicon-based optical signal processing techniques, including high wavelength selectivity, (de)multiplexing and complex modulation formats, have been implemented along with the matured RF technology to format cost-size-effective systems to achieve high performance and robust communications links.

The proposed optical heterodyne-based module is illustrated in Fig. 1(a), consisting of selective dual bandpass filters, and dual-parallel (DP) Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM) as the key components of the sub-THz transmitter system. The operating principle of this design is based on optical heterodyne, described as follows: light from an external optical frequency comb generator (OFCG) is used as the feed system to the proposed silicon module. Dual filtering is employed to select two single modes with a 100 GHz frequency difference. The combination of the two modes is realized via a 2x1 multimode interference coupler, after only the one of them has been modulated. This integrated system is offered utilizing TOWER Semiconductor’s silicon photonics platform. Fig. 1(b) depicts a photograph of the employed photonic integrated circuit, where dual filters and MZM are

Fig. 1. (a) The diagram of the proposed sub-THz wireless transmitter utilizing dual wavelength filters and DP MZM architecture when light from External OFCG is coupled in the input grating coupler (GC), (b) A photograph of the on-chip silicon transmitter module.

highlighted in white dashed circles. The integrated components are second-order filters of 100 GHz free spectral range (FSR) along with Quadrature Phase-Shift Keying (QPSK) optical modulator of 1 mm phase shifter length, allowing modulation-efficient signal processing in the optical THz domain. To the best of our knowledge, TOWER Semiconductor's integration platform is one of the very few open-access foundries that offers co-integration of discrete optical components to forge a complete low-loss system, highly co-operating along with the matured foundry's electronics platform. Additionally, the photonic integrated components were designed and optimized using the Synopsys's OptoCompiler platform that merges electronic and photonic design control over complex designs, ensuring an error-free photonic and Integrated Circuit (IC) design. Hereby, the designed SiPh subsystem proposes an efficient passive phase-locking circuit and a higher-order modulation scheme to serve as the cost-effective alternative for sub-THz wireless transmitter systems.

Next generation coherent optical THz communication systems require energy efficiency, channel integrity, and wide bandwidth. Thus, long-term stability can be achieved to establish robust wireless links. Cascaded ring resonator-based configurations as bandpass filters are designed to achieve high Q-factor, thus, high wavelength selectivity, narrow bandpass, and frequency-locked optical signal [8]. Therefore, single and serially coupled filter configurations are investigated. As part of future flexible wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) systems, flat-top (or box-like) filter response characteristics are desirable include high stopband rejection, thus, low crosstalk between channels and insertion loss. Wavelength and bandwidth tunability can be also achieved through the higher-order filters [9]. Similar responses have been accomplished on this study. The proposed single and double filter geometries offer a free spectral range (FSR) of 100 GHz with total length of 713.8 μm and 750 μm , respectively. To satisfy the full FSR tunability requirement, the shifter configurations are based on a custom heater element and phase shifters of 266.68 μm utilizing thermo-optic and plasma dispersion effect,

respectively. Moreover, the serially coupled dual filter supports the individual tuning per ring-filter as well as the tunability of the optical coupling power between the single ring-filters. The tuning of the power-splitting ratio is realized on an integrated tunable directional coupler utilizing a transversely induced thermal effect towards the waveguide via an integrated heater. The heater is placed at 500 μm over the waveguide with a distance offset of $d = 0.5 \mu\text{m}$, displaying the desired phase velocity mismatch on the coupled modes, changing the cross-coupled power between the waveguides, as it is successfully investigated [10].

In coherent optical communication schemes, advanced modulation formats and WDM are essential technologies to expand network functionality and achieve higher channel capacity. Integrated Si-based MZMs in a parallel configuration are introduced for IQ modulation [6]. On the next chapter, a single MZM is tested, similar to the nested modulator in the DP MZM configuration, owing a length of 2 mm. The single MZM owns lumped electrodes of total length of 2 mm and is under testing for amplitude modulation. The desirable phase shift in each arm is realized though a carrier depletion based PN junction to induce the modulated transmitted signal. While the capabilities of this integrated platform are demonstrated in this paper, more complex components, such as the QPSK modulator proposed, are currently tested in advanced modulation formats to support high-level RF signal processing.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Discrete building blocks of the silicon-based sub-THz transmitter are tested. Single and dual filters are implemented for mode demultiplexing and a MZM for optical signal modulation. All tested integrated optical components are part of a 5x5 mm chip and are accessed via 18 μm grating couplers.

A. Wavelength Filtering

Integrated filters operating as wavelength selectors or demultiplexers must display the ideal filter spectral profile. By increasing the number of the resonator-based structures, the "box-like" spectra can be attained. The parameter that defines the box-like filter response is the shape factor (SF) which is the ratio of the -1 dB to the -10 dB bandwidth. Table 1 summarizes the reported performance of the fundamental metrics for both single and dual filters of the same coupling constant of $k=0.125$. On the first column, the experimental results are reported from the heater element, displaying great tunability performance as well as Synopsys OptoCompiler's capabilities to support custom designs. In the next two columns, single and dual filters achieve phase modulation via plasma dispersion effect. In the next two columns, single and dual filters achieve phase modulation via plasma dispersion effect. Thus, with an applied voltage, the depletion region width of the PN junction increases altering waveguide properties, e.g., inducing the change in the effective refractive index. Inevitable optical losses in the output amplitude and shape factor are anticipated since the absorption coefficient changes along with carrier density. Filtering performances of the first-ever integration on the TOWER Semiconductor's

SiPh platform are summarized, indicating great potential for optical signal processing. From the first two columns regarding the two tuning mechanisms on the single filter, wavelength tunability over the 100 GHz range and -3dB bandwidth down to 15 GHz are achieved. Single and dual filters show high wavelength selectivity across the full FSR (100 GHz) with tuning efficiency of 0.02 nm/mW and up to 24 GHz with 0.005 nm/mW, respectively. In the case of serially coupled rings, the limited tuning range is probably due to the insertion loss under the biasing condition. At the last row of the table, the loss in dB is reported for achievable wavelength tuning in comparison to the 0 Volt condition. Regarding the dual filters, less loss is measured as the reachable tuning range was smaller than the full FSR.

Table 1. Calculated parameters of the single and dual filter responses.

Parameters	Single	Single	Dual	Units
Tuning mechanism	Thermo-optic	Plasma dispersion	Plasma dispersion	
Shape factor	0.22	0.28	0.27 - 0.66	
BW @-3dB	15	17.5	12.48	GHz
BW tunability	-	-	12.48 - 32.5	GHz
Extinction Ratio	18	17.5	42.3 - 30	dB
Q-factor	5000	5535.71	5961.5 - 4300	
Wavelength tuning	Full FSR	Full FSR	1/4 Full FSR	
Tuning efficiency	0.02	0.44	0.005	nm/mW
Loss (for full FSR)	0.57	9.93	4.64	dB

In the case of plasma dispersion tuning effect, insertion losses show higher impact than in the thermo-optic effect. The reason behind these losses is primarily attributed to the absorption resulting from their substantial dependence on the hole concentration [11]. Additionally, the strong correlation between the extinction ratio (ER), SF and -3dB bandwidth of the passband dual-filter is demonstrated below. In Fig. 2(a), the box-like filter shape from the second order filter is shown, at a centered wavelength of $\lambda=1550\text{nm}$ with a passband ripple of $<1\text{ dB}$. However, the misalignment of the two resonances reveals the coupling strength condition between cavities and probable scattering losses due to waveguide sidewalls. Therefore, there is a shift of each filter's resonant wavelength that can be adjusted and eliminated at the desirable coupling condition of the two individual responses. Thus, enhanced filtering characteristics are proven over the desirable coupling condition: Q-factor increase close to 6000 and a 20 GHz bandwidth range resulting in almost two times higher extinction ratio, reaching a high stopband rejection of 42.3 dB. The overall dependence of these parameters is investigated in Fig. 2(b), while two phase shifters of each filter are biased with the same voltage step in reverse. The desirable coupling condition, where constructive interference of both resonances occur, is given for a total power of 2.67 mW (P_1+P_2).

Fig. 2. (a) Measured bandwidth tunability of the dual filter for band ripple less than 1 dB, and (b) Tuning of shape factor and extinction ratio as a function of the 3-dB bandwidth, as phase shifters of each filter are biased with the same voltage step in reverse.

The tuning efficiency of the bandwidth is equal to 0.13 nm/mW, calculated for the centered wavelength.

B. Single Mach-Zehnder Modulator

The optical response of a single MZM has been performed under a data transmission test [12]. The experimental setup can be seen in Fig. 3(a). For the given phase shifter length of 2 mm, the modulator efficiency is calculated at 1.8 V*cm, obtained by the transfer function of the MZM. To achieve data over-fiber transmission, a pseudo-random bit sequence (PRBS) with a length of 27-1 is implemented and amplified as the input driving RF signal. It is applied via DC probe needles, adding a limitation factor in the electrical bandwidth to effectively test the modulator response. While the modulator is biased at the quadrature transmission point, operating within its linear range, an output data stream of 4 Gbps has been transmitted successfully. Fig. 3(b) displays the recorded eye-diagrams taken from a bit-error rate tester (BERT) for BER computing and eye-diagram analysis. The signal degradation is due to electrode driving scheme. Since lumped electrodes are used, the modulation efficiency is considered limited since the signals are propagated to a small region and are less effective for high-frequency operation. In the future, the design of traveling-wave electrodes is already considered to support higher modulation efficiency and better control of the

Fig. 3. a) Experimental setup for BER estimation from the single MZM. Red and black solid lines depict electrical and optical path, respectively. PC: polarization controller, OPM: optical power meter, PD: photodiode. b) Optical transmission data via the single MZM modulator. An eye diagram for (i) 1.5 Gbps, (ii) 3 Gbps, (iii) 4 Gbps, and (iv) 4.5 Gbps data transmissions are demonstrated at a received power of -45 dBm.

electrical signal. As the next step, having these results under consideration, the electro-optic response of a more complex circuit, i.e., DP MZM nested in the proposed optical transmitter module, will be tested on amplitude and frequency modulation schemes.

IV. CONCLUSION

Photonic integration represents a versatile solution for the realization of THz transmitter systems introducing new possibilities on systems complexity along with the RF technology. The discrete components of the proposed IC on the currently developing TOWER's SiPh platform have been proven to operate efficiently in terms of channel integrity, and optical modulation capabilities. Integrated single wavelength filters have achieved full FSR tunability of 100 GHz and up to 24 GHz in the double cascade configuration, reaching a high stopband rejection of 42.3 dB. Data transmission up to 4 Gbps has been detected successfully by a single-ended PD. Thus, a sub-THz wireless transmitter to support phase-locked optical signals and multi-level modulation schemes can be a promising system solution to reach the low phase noise and high-quality RF signal.

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